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Grahani Roga management by Ayurveda principles and lifestyle modification

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Abstract

Grahani is an ayurveda terms related to the seat of *agni* (digestive fire), which help in the metabolism and digestion of food. The ancient text of ayurveda described that ingestion, digestion, absorption and assimilation of *Aahaar* is regulated by *Grahani*. When this *Agni* becomes *mandagni* then improper digestion of ingested food leads pathological condition termed as *Grahaniroga*. Similarly *Trividh* anomalies of the *Jatharagni* also termed as *Grahanidosha*. *Grahani* is a disease which affects large population globally especially in developing country and associated with improper food habits along with stressful lifestyle. The pathogenesis of *Grahani roga* works around *Agni dosha* which associated with impaired digestive function of digestive fire. Ayurveda described various treatment modalities for the management of *Grahaniroga* such as; use of herbs & formulation, *yoga* and life style modification. Present article summarized ayurveda perspective of *Grahani roga* and its management by Ayurveda principles and lifestyle modification.

Keywords: Ayurveda; *Grahani*; *Agnidosha*; Yoga; Lifestyle; Colitis

1. Introduction

*Grahani Dosh*a is a common problem specially affects people living with unhygienic conditions and suffered with nutritional deficiency. The faulty lifestyle, consumption of junk food, stress, Inadequate sleep and avoidance of *Sadvritta* are the major reasons of *Grahani Dosh*a. Pathologically disease initiates due to the improper digestion of food which further vitiate *Agni* and *Dosh*as leading to formation of *ama* which further resulted symptoms of constipation and diarrhea(1-4).Drugs having *Kashaya Rasa*, *Ushna Veerya*, *Madhura Vipaka* & *Ruksha Guna* help to pacifies *Vata* & *Pitta Dosh*a therefore potentiates *Agni* which improves process of digestion. Drugs which gives bulk to the stool, hydrate body and possess nutritional benefits also relieve symptoms of *Grahani Dosh*a. Ayurveda text emphasized on four types of *Grahani Dosh*a as mentioned in Figure 1. This article described general consideration of *Grahani Dosh*a and its management by ayurveda and conduction of disciplinary lifestyle(2-7).

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Figure 1 Types of Grahani

2. Etiological Factors

- Abhojanat, Ajeernabhojanat, Attibhojanaat, Visamasanat, Asatmya, Guru, Ruksha, etc.
- Vyadhi karshanat and Vega vidharana
- Stress, anxiety and grief
- Indisciplinary lifestyle and bad food habits
- Unhygienic environmental condition
- Nutritional insufficiency
- Diseased condition which weakened Agni
- Virudha-ahara
- Avoidance of concept of Desha and kala during consumption of food stuffs
- Excessive use of antibiotics.

3. Symptoms

According to *Acharaya* the predominant symptoms of disease are; *Aalasya*, *Trishna*, *Aanvidaah*, *ChirPakka*, *Balakshaya* and *Gaurvam*, etc. Other symptoms of diseases are *Aruchi*, *Kasa*, *Karnakshveda* and *Antrakunjana*. Intestinal spasms, diarrhea, constipation and abdominal pain also observed in acute condition⁽⁶⁻⁸⁾.

3.1. Ayurveda management of grahanidosha

- The traditional text of Ayurveda suggested that *Grahani Dosh*a may be treated by following concept of *Langhana* and using *Deepana* and *Pachana* medicines which help to potentiate *Agni* and eliminate *ama*.
- Purgation therapy with stimulant drugs also helps to remove *Ama*
- *Triphala Churna* help in evacuation of stool.
- Buttermilk (*Takra*) also suggested by ancient *Acharya* for treatment of *Grahani*.

Table 1 Specific Ayurveda treatment for Grahani roga

Sr.No.	Treatment	Beneficial effects
1	Niruhabasti, Virechana and Anuvasanbasti	Remove symptoms of Vataja grahani
2	Chandanadyaghritam, Tikataghrita	Pacifies Pittaja grahani
3	Pippalyadyadi choorna	Treat Kaphaja grahani
4	Nagaradi kwatha	Pacifies vitiated Vata thus help in Vataja grahani
5	Madhukasava, Duralabhasava,	Relieve Kaphaja grahani
6	Panhchmuladya Taila	Help to manage Vataja grahani
7	Haridradya Kshara, Duralabhadyakshara	Treat Kaphaja grahani
8	Abhayadikashaya	Suggested for Vataja grahani

3.2. Life style modification in *grahani*

Modification in lifestyle and balanced diet regime along with consideration of *Pathya Apathya* help to cure *Grahani*.

3.3. Diet modification

- Modification in diet pattern towards the healthy eating habits boosts *Agni* and prevents chances of *Grahani*.
- *Virudha-ahara* must be avoided; means one should consume diet as per his/her internal constitution by following concept of *Desha* and *Kala*.
- Ayurveda mentioned balanced diet under *Sansarjana Krama* with routine diet plan depending on the *Prakriti* of the individual. Thus patient of *Grahani* recommended to follow diet pattern of *Sansarjana Krama*.
- Meal should be consumed at regular intervals.
- Junk foods, allergic foods and food difficult to digest should be avoided.
- Diet containing balanced nutritional value need to be adopted.

3.4. Dietary materials recommended for *Grahani roga* are as follows:

Diet which promote digestive enzyme; restore normal flora and maintain nutritional sufficiency should be adopted such as; fibers, fruit, vegetables, grains and curd.

- Yavagu, Panchkola soup
- Takrarista, Jangalmansa
- Vegetable soups
- Light diet
- Pineapple, Papaya, Oranges and Lemon

3.5. Behavior modification

- Behavioral factors such as fear, grief, stress and sleeplessness may also lead symptoms of *Grahani*. Therefore one should avoid stress, fear and grief to disrupt condition of depression which may affect *Agni*.
- Habits of too much thinking/*Chintan* should be avoided which may affect process of digestion since during thinking process blood circulation remain associated with brain mainly instead of intestine.
- One should consume diet by following rules of *Swasthwarita* in proper manner so to achieve maximum beneficial effect of consumed food⁽⁷⁻⁹⁾.
- One should remain positive and enthusiastic to maintain normal metabolic functioning.
- One should always think that the food which he/she going to consume will offers good effect.

3.6. Daily regimen modification/Exercise and yoga

- Day time sleeping and late night awakening should be avoided.
- One should follow daily regimen with fix timing of each and every activities including fix daily routine of

exercise, breakfast, meal and sleep.

- Regular exercise to strengthen body & *Agni*.
- Meditation to calm down stress.
- *Yoga* and *Pranayama* also offers beneficial effect to increase stress resistance.
- Ayurveda mentioned some defined regimen such as; *Ritucharya* and *Dinacharya* to get beneficial results of daily regimen.
- *Dhyana* and *Shodhna* procedure after some fix interval also offers beneficial effect in *Grahani*⁽⁷⁻¹⁰⁾.

3.7. Role of Asana in Grahani

- *Suryanamaskara* – Improves metabolic activities
- *Bhujangasana*: *Bhujangasana* heat the body and improves digestion.
- *Mayurasana*: *Mayurasana* removes undigested material in stomach.
- *Paschimottanasana*: *Paschimottanasana* boosts gastric fire.
- *Matsyendrasana*: *Matsyendrasana* stimulates *jatharagni*.
- *Sarvangasana*: *Sarvangasana* pacifies *Kapha* & *Pitta*, also relief indigestion.

4. Conclusion

Grahani is disease of *Annavaha strotas* related to *Agni* and lifestyle pattern. Ayurveda considers *Grahani* as *Tridoshatmaka* disease of digestive fire occurs due to the vitiation of *Agni*; *Jatharagni*, *SamanVayu*, *Pachak Pitta* and *Kledaka Kapha*. Disease characterized by abdominal pain, bloating and disturbed bowel habits. Ayurveda offers wide range of formulations and therapeutic modalities along with suggestions to modify lifestyle pattern which overall offers beneficial effects in the management of *Grahani roga*.

Compliance with ethical standards

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